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Views on Preserving the Indigenous Cultural Values of the Hmong People in the Northern Midland and Mountainous Provinces of Vietnam

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Astract:

The article interviewed 245 village leaders in the Hmong ethnic community and local government officials and leaders in the northern midlands and mountainous areas of Vietnam. The northern midland and mountainous provinces are home to 90% of ethnic Hmong people across the country, which is an area imbued with Hmong cultural identity, in line with the topic of this study. The study focused on understanding the beauty of culture, the results of preserving indigenous cultural values, and the support of authorities in the process of preserving Hmong culture from the perspective of local communities and policy leaders. From there, appropriate recommendations are made.

Keywords: *Preserving cultural values, Hmong culture, midlands and northern mountains.*

1. Introduction

The 21st century is arguably the century of globalization (U. Hani et al., 2012). Despite all the benefits brought to the economy, globalization is seen as a threat factor to cultural assimilation (Grazuleviciute, 2006). Culture is an important driver of urban economic development (Songjie et al., 2011). Therefore, the preservation of precious cultural values is becoming increasingly important in the current context. Indeed, cultural heritage is becoming increasingly important not only due to its economic benefits but is also seen as a more sustainable approach. As rural and remote economies go through difficult periods of change, for some local communities, cultural heritage can help economically (Günlü, 2009).

In Vietnam, culture is a matter of special concern to our Party and State. In recent years, our country is in the process of international economic integration. Along with the process of economic integration, many complex social issues also arise, especially cultural issues. In addition to customs with a long history, many new types of culture have greatly influenced the social life of our country. In the new social context, our Party has been renewing policies for preserving cultural values in order to meet the needs of cultural and spiritual activities of a part of the people, while maintaining social stability, creating necessary conditions for national development.

Under the impact of globalization as well as economic development, the traditional culture of the Hmong people has changed markedly. It is expressed on aspects such as familial, kinship, social relationships; the role of people with prestige, religious beliefs, rituals in marriage, funerals, culture, lifestyle, etc. The current issue is how, in the conditions of global integration and rapid economic development, still preserve and promote the cultural values of the Hmong ethnic group, contributing to the construction of an advanced culture, imbued with national cultural identity in the spirit of the 5th Central Resolution VIII and continue to implement according to the Central Resolution. 9th course on building and developing Vietnamese culture and people to meet the requirements of sustainable development of the country.

On the other hand, changes in demographics, economic growth and tourism, and technological improvements have impacted the preservation of the indigenous cultural values of the Hmong ethnic community in the northern region of Vietnam. Cultural heritage is the main attraction of the tourism industry - the main economic source of Hmong ethnic communities living in the northern midlands and mountainous areas. Necessary. In particular, in recent years, a part of Hmong people in the northern midland and mountainous provinces of Vietnam have abandoned long-standing cultural values such as ancestor worship and traditional cultural customs and lifestyles of their people, causing confusion and difficulties in cultural preservation activities.

In order to solve this problem, the study delved into the views of local Hmong communities in the northern midland and mountainous provinces in order to capture the awareness and opinions of indigenous people about the preservation of Hmong cultural values. From there, the study finds out the peculiarities of the culture of the Hmong people, the need to preserve their culture in the new period. In addition, the study also explores perspectives from officials and leaders of local governments to have a more multidimensional and comprehensive view, especially on strategies to preserve cultural values for the Hmong people. From there, the study makes appropriate recommendations.

2. Theoretical basis

2.1. The concept of culture

2.1.1. Concept of culture

Culture is a multi-meaning concept and explaining culture is quite a complex one. In the 18th century, culture first emerged as a sociological concept representing the elite (Bakhtin, 1981). In 1871, Tylor introduced the modern concept of culture as a collection of diverse and characteristic activities of human society. Culture includes all the mental, material, intellectual, and emotional characteristics that characterize a society or group of people. It manifests itself through lifestyles, customs, beliefs, art, and other value systems. Since then, culture simulates human life in a rational and critical way. As a result, people are aware of their own abilities and constantly learn and create outstanding achievements. In the face of the continuous development of society, the role of culture is increasingly promoted. In 2010, UNESCO made culture one of the four pillars of Sustainable Development along with social inclusion, economic growth and environmental balance (UNESCO Agenda 21, 2010).

In Vietnam, culture is understood as the level of culture, education, and lifestyle of a social organization. In that sense, culture is the expression that characterizes the level of development of a stage. It encompasses all the material and spiritual values created by people in each particular society in service of their lives. Culture can also be understood in a broader sense that ranges from modern sophisticated products to beliefs, customs, lifestyles and labor. According to Pham Van Dong (1994), he defines culture as reflecting throughout the entire history of the nation, which survives after many turbulences and rapids to constantly develop and grow. Therefore, culture is the soul, the intense vitality of a people. President Ho Chi Minh (1943) stated his view that culture includes all that man creates and invents as a means of survival as well as the purpose of life. No

includes language, writing, ethics, law, science, religion, literature, art, tools for daily living in terms of food, shelter and modes of use.

Summing up the above views, according to the author, culture is the set of all material and spiritual values accumulated in the process of labor and human development. Cultural values are handed down from generation to generation and gradually ingrained in people's consciousness. Therefore, culture is the key to the development of society.

2.1.2. Features of culture

The four characteristics of culture include:

- Systematicity

Systematicity expressed in culture is an entity that covers all life, economic and social activities, performing the function of social organization. Thanks to its systematic nature, culture expresses the close connections between the phenomena of its characteristics, the laws of its formation and development. This increases the stability of society.

- Calculate value

Culture is valuable because it is a measure of all levels of humanity of society and people. In terms of purpose, cultural values can be material values (serving material needs) and spiritual values (serving spiritual needs). Besides, in terms of meaning, culture implies the value of use, moral values and aesthetic values. It is also possible to distinguish into eternal price and transient value according to the factor of time. Thanks to its value, culture performs the function of social adjustment, maintaining dynamic equilibrium to constantly improve and adapt to changes in the environment. From there, it serves as a basis for adjusting norms, creating a driving force for the development of society.

- Humanity

Humanity manifests itself in culture as the rope that connects people with people, it performs the function of communication and has the effect of linking them together. If language is the form of communication then culture is its content.

- Historicity

Culture is the red thread throughout the process of labor and development of human society. So culture is historical. Cultural values are accumulated and recreated in the community through space and time, molded into social patterns and fixed in the form of language, customs, customs, rituals, laws. Historicity creates a culture of breadth and depth.

2.2. The concept of cultural preservation

Conservation is understood as retaining not to lose. That is, the purposes of protecting, preserving, preserving the existence of things and phenomena, preserving them to exist with time. To preserve things and phenomena is to preserve, not to make them fade, change and deform.

On this basis, cultural preservation is understood as efforts to protect and preserve the existence of heritage in its original form. Not only preserving, conservation is associated with the mission of putting cultural values into practice without fading over time. And those good traditional cultural values are spread, shine and have positive meaning in the social life of the people, contributing to cultural goals in socio-economic development. Moreover, the preservation of cultural heritage must not only aim at tangible values but must also include intangible values such as language, art, style, etc.

2.3. The meaning of cultural preservation

Firstly, cultural preservation is both a goal and a driving force for sustainable socio-economic development. Culture expresses the unique identity of the community and is considered the norm, a measure of humanity, humanity of people and society at certain historical moments. On the other hand, culture serves people but when absorbed by people in real life, Through its organizational, regulatory and social education functions, it is cultural values that have the opposite effect on people, causing society and people to constantly be adjusted, mobilized and developed in a better and better direction. Therefore, culture is both the spiritual foundation of society and also a strong endogenous motivation and resource promoting the economic and social development of any country, nation or locality. At the Resolution of the 5th Central Committee of the Eighth Party Central Committee on Building and Developing an advanced Vietnamese culture, imbued with national identity, our Party stated: "Culture is the spiritual foundation of society, as well as the goal, as well as a driving force for socio-economic development". Once the nation lacks a progressive and healthy spiritual foundation, and does not care about addressing the relationship between economic development and progress and social justice, it will not be possible to achieve the sustainable development goals. Therefore, culture is not only the crystallized product of economic activity, but also the driving force of socio-economic development.

Secondly, preserving cultural values plays an important role in the process of sustainable socio-economic development of ethnic minority areas. Ethnic minorities have access to and enjoy basic social services at a very low level compared to the general level of the whole country. In addition, the factors of human resource quality, population quality and economic production practices lag behind. Many customs, customs, superstitions tend to develop. Many outstanding cultural values are being lost, etc., which are also major obstacles to the sustainable socio-economic development of ethnic minorities in our country. The work of preserving and promoting the traditional cultural values of the people, especially the restoration and development of traditional crafts, the preservation and restoration of festivals, costumes and other cultural forms, folklore, preservation of national languages, etc. is considered one of the key tasks and very important solutions to successfully determine the goal of sustainable socio-economic development of ethnic minority areas according to the market mechanism. Over the years, committees and authorities at all levels have paid special attention to the preservation and promotion of traditional cultural values of ethnic minorities associated with the cause of cultural preservation and development, especially the goal of national cultural development.

2.4. Some features of Vietnamese Hmong culture

Located in a multi-ethnic country, the Hmong ethnic group is considered an important member of the ethnic community in Viet Nam. Hmong ethnic groups usually reside at an altitude of 800 to 1500 m above sea level including most of the northern mountainous provinces in a fairly large area, along the Vietnam-China and Vietnam-Laos borders from Lang Son to Nghe An, which are concentrated mainly in the provinces of East and Northwest of Vietnam such as: Ha Giang, Lao Cai, Lai Chau, Son La... Due to nomadic practices, some Hmong people in the 1980s and 1990s migrated as far as the Central Highlands, scattered in some parts of Gia Lai and Kon Tum.

According to the 2019 Population and Housing Census, the Hmong people in Vietnam have a population of 1,393,547 people, ranking 6th in the list of ethnic groups in Vietnam, residing in 62 out of 63 provinces and cities. In particular, the majority of Hmong people live in the northern midland and mountainous provinces. The number of Hmong people living in 7 provinces in this region accounts for 85% of the number nationwide, respectively: Ha Giang (292,677 people, accounting for 31.9% of the province's population and 21.7% of the total number of Hmong people in Vietnam), Dien Bien (228,279 people, accounting for 34.8% of the province's

population and 16.0% of the total number of Hmong people in Vietnam), Son La (200,480 people, accounting for 14.6% of the province's population and 14.7% of the total Hmong population in Vietnam), Lao Cai (183,172 people, accounting for 23.8% of the province's population, 13.7% of the total number of Hmong people in Vietnam), Lai Chau (110,323 people), Yen Bai (107,049 people), Cao Bang (61,579 people).

Hmong areas often have markets. The market meets every 6 days (some places every 5 days). The exchange of goods on the basis of facilities for things, using very little exchange currency. The market is both a place to exchange goods and a place to meet all walks of life. In particular, there is a market with cultural characteristics of the Hmong people, which is the "Love Market". The love market is held once a year. Sapa Love Market, is a place to attract domestic and foreign tourists to learn about this unique culture. Hmong people have jewelry: earrings, necklaces, bracelets, copper rings, silver rings, gold rings. If there are 2 rings on the hand, the person is married or married. Women like to use beautiful color umbrellas, which both cover the rain, shade the sun and make jewelry for themselves, creating charm. Nowadays, H'mong women's clothing has changed: H'mong Sapa women wear short and narrow trousers, double outerwear with a hard neck that burns patterns. H'mong White Son La women wear long trousers, white blouses on the inside, and traditional shirts on the outside. H'mong Hoa women wear open-armspit shirts.

Linen weaving is one of the unique production activities of the Hmong people. They developed a variety of crafts such as knitting, forging, making horse saddles, woodwork, especially containers; making paper copies, silver jewelry to serve the needs and tastes of the people.

Hmong people have a diverse and rich spiritual life in terms of customs, religious beliefs and writing, voice, culture and art. Among the community of 54 ethnic groups of Vietnam, the Hmong ethnic group is one of the ethnic groups that is less susceptible to the traditional cultural identity of the nation. Hmong culture is an element of Vietnamese culture, their unique cultural identity has contributed and enriched Vietnamese culture. In the current period of international integration, in order to develop "integration" without dissolution or loss of identity, the preservation of national culture requires research, enthusiasm, perseverance and long-term. In this way, cultural values will forever be preserved and promoted.

3. Research Methodology

Group interviews and in-depth interviews were the primary methods used to collect data in this study. The objective of the interviews was to explore respondents' views on issues related to Hmong cultural values and explain why they thought so. The interviewees were Hmong community leaders such as village elders, village chiefs, village heads and officials as well as government leaders in provincial communes and districts in Hmong areas.

Specifically, based on the Census of Housing (General Statistics Office, 2019), the study selected 7 provinces with many Hmong people residing in the North of Vietnam to approach interviews, Ha Giang, Dien Bien, Son La, Lao Cai, Lai Chau, Yen Bai and Cao Bang respectively.

The study studied and contacted 425 people by phone or with the help of local authorities, but only 245 people interviewed (57.6%). The interviews were conducted with the help of 2 Hmong ethnic research facilitators to interpret and communicate in native language cases, while creating a sense of familiarity and comfort for the interviewees. The data collection is conducted for 3 years from 2019 to 2021, then encrypted with the help of Nvivo software.

In terms of demographics, participants are classified by age, position and religion. In terms of age, people in the 40-45 age group accounted for the most (38.7%), followed by the 35-40 group (24.9%). The group from 45 to 50 years old is also quite high, accounting for 18.3%. The fact that the subjects focused heavily on middle age

was quite plausible because the subjects of this study were village elders, village heads, officials and leaders, who had many years of living and working in Hmong communities, more clearly grasping the problems in indigenous culture. In terms of positions, there were 90 village heads/village heads participating, reaching the largest number (36.7%), followed by about 67 village elders (27.5%), 38 commune/district officials (15.5%) and 50 leaders of communes and provinces. In terms of religion, the number of protestants accounts for 33.7%, the proportion in other religious categories is quite even.

Table 1. Demographics of group interview participants

Character	Amount	Proportion
Age range		
< 35	37	15,0%
[35,40)	61	24,9%
[40, 45)	95	38,7%
[45, 50)	45	18,3%
> 50	8	3,1%
Duty		
Village elders	67	27,5%
Village chief/village head	90	36,7%
Commune/district officials	38	15,5%
Commune leaders	28	11,3%
Provincial leaders	22	9,0%
Religion		
Protestantism	83	33,7%
Cults and animists	43	17,5%
Satanism	38	15,5%
Different	36	14,7%
Without	46	18,6%
Sum	245	100%

Source: survey research

4. Research results

The interviews are prepared before the question based on three main contents: awareness of indigenous cultural values, preservation of cultural values and the government assistance.

4.1. Awareness of indigenous cultural values of the Hmong people

The issues of cultural values in this study were presented according to the perceptions of Hmong community leaders in the southern provinces. North Vietnam. The frequency of words used by the subjects will be instrumental in determining the level of awareness of the Hmong community about indigenous cultural values. Geo. The classification and analysis of the frequency of words used is based on the respondent's answer.

The interview results showed that the understanding of the concept of cultural values was incomplete and the degree was not the same in the subjects studied. In general, interviewees use different keywords to describe cultural values. A total of 15 phrases with the most frequency are used to answer this question:

Table 2. How often words refer to the concept of cultural values in the interview

Expression	Frequency	Expression	Frequency	Expression	Frequency
<i>Custom</i>	7%	<i>Tradition</i>	5,70%	<i>Building</i>	4,20%
<i>Habit</i>	6,80%	<i>Costumes</i>	5,30%	<i>Lifestyle</i>	3,70%
<i>Community</i>	6,50%	<i>Gastronomy</i>	5,10%	<i>Ceremonies</i>	3,20%
<i>Legacy</i>	6,40%	<i>Music, folk dance</i>	4,90%	<i>Activity</i>	3,20%
<i>Beliefs</i>	5,70%	<i>Festivals</i>	4,80%	<i>Regulation</i>	2,80%

Source: survey research

The cultural aspects offered by the interview subjects are quite diverse, including customs, beliefs, costumes, cuisine, music, festive activities, rituals, temple heritages, architectural works, etc. In general, although not directly mentioned, the cultural values mentioned can be divided into 2 main groups: intangible cultural values and intangible culture.

Not big, massive or luxurious, solid houses. Hmong ethnic houses have unique and outstanding architecture because behind the houses are ways of adaptation and national values that have been maintained for generations of descendants. For the Hmong people, housing is a place to protect, dwell and store the sacred features of the clan.

"Hmong houses have unique and different architecture hidden deep into the layers of bricks and stones are the customs, culture and beliefs of the people of the highlands." (Village head, 34 years old, Ha Giang province).

"Hmong houses usually have 3 rooms, the kitchen fireplace warms the whole house, the nave is straight with the main door is the earth, ancestral worship room and a kitchen for cooking. For the Hmong, the person in the house must be suitable for the earth, the land of the land." (village elder, 48 years old, Yen Bai province).

"The economy is growing, the cross-cultural interaction has caused the Hmong housing to also change gradually, cement roofing for red tiles and concrete bricks, modern materials to save human energy are also used by people. Although there is some influence of modern life, the ancient architecture of the Hmong people is still there." (leader of Lao Cai province)

Regarding temples and shrines, Hmong people have very unique and diverse stone worship beliefs. For the Hmong people, the incarnate stone becomes the ancestral stone, the grandparents' stone, the guardian god for each Hmong family. There are families who choose ancestral stones outside the cornfield, because they wish the ancestral stones would protect the crop from wild animals and bless the bountiful harvest. Meanwhile, the majority choose ancestral stones that are close to their homes and, as a result, ancestral stones protect people, homes, gardens and pets.

"Stone worship is a unique culture that shows the cohesion and connection between stone and people, a community of people who have for generations 'lived on rocks, died buried in stones'." (village elder 52 years old, Dien Bien province)

"From cold, rough mountain rock, through the hands of the Hmong, to a beautiful but solid stone fence, sheltering small houses. Stones are also carved as living items: stone mortars, bathtubs. The rocks keep the corn firm against the wind and rain." (56-year-old village elder).

"Here, stone worship is not merely a form of belief or a spiritual cultural practice but can be seen as an inevitable consequence of the cultural-ecological relationship," (38-year-old commune official).

The intangible cultural values mentioned include art culture, beliefs, customs, festivals, food culture. The traditional dress of Hmong women includes: "skirt, bra, bib, with a *cloth covering the front and small square fabric covering the back, belt, head scarf, leggings*" while men wear "*underarm and chest slit, usually with 4 bags, 4 buttons, lame leg-cut tights.*"

The Hmong people have a rich folklore treasure trove with genres such as: Fables, jokes, folk songs, school songs, love songs, orphan songs, wedding songs (xin, etc.), dao songs, proverbs, citadels, etc., reflecting the worldview, human life and working life and struggle of the Hmong people.

"The explanations of the spiritual life of the Hmong people are as much as ghosts, offerings, women who are not allowed to go upstairs, offering poles, and dancing as guides in family life and life in general." (46-year-old village head, Cao Bang province).

In terms of music, Hmong instruments are quite unique, with trumpets, flutes and instruments such as trumpets, the lip guitar, although simple, emit mysterious and attractive sounds.

"Hoarse is used in funerals and some family rituals"(55-year-old village elder, Lai Chau province)

"When you go on the road or when you rest in the night, in the moonlight after a hard day, the boys often sing hoarse dances." (village elder 52 years old, Ha Giang province)

"Lips and trumpets are also a means of exchanging feelings for men and women." (village elder 58 years old, Ha Giang province)

In terms of beliefs, unlike the Vietnamese and Tay people, most Hmong families do not set up their own ancestral altars. The place of worship is just a rectangular sheet of paper on the back wall of the nave. The place of worship is a sacred place, only the head of the family can invite ancestors and sons to approach. Hmong people only worship their ancestors on New Year's Day, new rice or when offering healing. This is an important belief of the Hmong people, which worships grandparents, parents and deceased fellows who in their conception are within three generations.

Regarding the festival, in a year, Hmong people have two big Tet holidays: New Year and May 5. *"Tet is the most important new year of the Hmong community, it is a sacred time for Hmong people to remember their ancestors, express gratitude to heaven and earth for harvesting crops and pray for a lush New Year's crop"* – 61-year-old village elder, Son La province.

In terms of food culture, Hmong people rely on food sources from farming, animal husbandry, and exploitation of natural products. In the past, they used to eat ground corn cooked into flour or half-cooked. Usually, they eat plain rice in the way of preparing things in a wooden hut. The majority of dishes are mainly prepared in the way of boiling or stir-frying. The meats if there is a lot of fresh food do not run out, they usually save by drying to on the torn stove (kitchen trellis). Hmong people shovel food with wooden spoons, using chopsticks is only secondary. *"When there are women who are not allowed to sit down to eat together, the host always sits on top, with his back to the back wall of the nave."* On market days, the people often cook, the Hmong people love to drink wine, especially corn wine distilled by themselves.

It can be seen that the culture of life of the Hmong people is very diverse and rich. The cultural values of the people here play an important role in the daily life, in the beliefs and way of life of the Hmong people without being confused with the cultural features of any other ethnic group. According to the storytelling and confiding of the villagers, it can be seen that the Hmong people bring both pride and intense love to the cultural values they have.

The role of cultural values is also viewed from a deeper perspective, mainly through the views of commune and provincial leaders participating in interviews. For them, cultural values are both the spiritual foundation of the Hmong community, as well as a strong endogenous motivation and resource to promote the economic and social development of the locality.

"Culture is the goal of development because culture created by people, which governs all human activities, is a production activity that provides spiritual energy for people, making people more and more perfect." (leader of Yen Bai province).

"Culture is the spiritual foundation of society, and at the same time the goal of development" (ha Giang provincial officials).

"The creative and developmental potential of society lies in the elements that constitute culture, that is, in the will to self-reliance, self-reliance and the ability to understand, in the soul, morality, lifestyle, aesthetic level of each individual and of the whole community." (Leader of Son La province)

In summary, Hmong is an ethnic minority community with characteristics of customs, lifestyles, beliefs, etc. that constitute a diverse and beautiful cultural value system. Hmong people (represented by the group interviewed) have pride and belief in those cultural values, have the will and desire to develop indigenous cultural values more and more completely.

4.2. Awareness of the preservation of indigenous cultural values of the Hmong people

According to the opinions of the participants, the implementation of cultural value preservation has been promoted and implemented by all levels, from provinces to localities, from localities to small ethnic communities such as villages, villages to households. The process of preserving cultural values does not stop at preserving but also aims at the communal goals of developing in a more civilized modern way. The preservation of values is combined with the development of modern society, creating very new cultures that are also very characteristic of the Hmong people.

Regarding the structure of houses of the Mong ethnic people, ground houses, three pavilions, planks, thatched roofs, tiles or boards and rituals in making houses such as choosing land, choosing directions, choosing wood are valued and they are also very interested in preserving the rituals related to the house.

"In general, the traditional housing of the Mong people is still relatively well preserved, with little variation." (officer of Yen Bai province)

In terms of costume, the Mong ethnic group preserves the national costume relatively well, especially women. Hmong women are hardworking, skillful, inheriting the embroidery work of the family or always bringing their own patterns of Hmong culture in their own and family clothes. However, there have also been intersections and transformations such as using industrial materials (fabric, embroidery thread) to sew costumes but the style is still the same.

"Up to now, Hmong women still embroider, use sewing machines, print beeswax to create patterns on costumes. During the holidays, Tet, they wear the best, latest (national costumes), wear a lot of jewelry to hang out." (lao cai village elder)

The traditional dances of the Hmong people are mainly religious dances: Hoarse dance, umbrella dance... Currently, these dances have been adapted and enhanced to become dances performed on stage, programs of mass art teams at the villages.

However, there are still limitations in the implementation of preserving cultural values for the Hmong community. Many cultural values have not been properly cared for, leading to gradual decline and loss. In folk performance art, the Hmong people have only a few folk songs: *"Strawberry singing, orphan singing; the songs of the hoarse, used to play the music of the dead at funerals, but now that the people who know how to wheeze and blow are less and less, the preservation of this art form is in danger of disappearing."* (officer of Yen Bai province)

In addition, although many cultural features have been preserved and changed in a more modern direction, they are not really radical. Many backward customs still appear and are continued, many beliefs and customs have the potential to endanger the lives of communities.

"The organization of funerals for the dead still has outdated practices such as: Shooting announces when someone dies; the deceased has not been put in a coffin, but left in the house for 3 to 7 days, etc." (59-year-old village elder, Dien Bien province)

"Some practices still exist in some areas: underage marriage, inbreeding." (leader of Ha Giang province)

The issue of housing planning in small communities has not been done well. Although roof houses and cottages are a unique feature of local people, the deteriorating housing situation, which cannot withstand rainstorms, affecting people's lives still exists.

On the other hand, the rapid development of current life, commercial trends and massive urban development plans cause concerns about cultural degradation. Locals believe that preserving culture can help keep the Hmong people's distinctive image from being degraded by uncontrolled developments and uncertainty. It is an ethnic group specializing in living in high mountainous areas, where the population is sparse but has its own characteristics of culture and natural beauty. Therefore, the lives of Hmong people are exploited for the purpose of tourism and trade development. But poor planning and management can create chaos in people's lives, preventing them from adapting to the development of a novel culture.

"Many temples of the village are surrounded by skyscrapers, living areas are confused with incompatible activities that make the soul of the village gradually disappear" -

"These centennial temples are surrounded by many other functional buildings. In the old days, the temple was a very quiet and sacred place. Many locations are surrounded by modern villas or tourist resorts."

In summary, the effective implementation of the preservation and promotion of Hmong national cultural values has been improved and implemented quite well when not only the attention and facilitation of the government but also the people have been aware of and understand the cultural values that generations of their people have created. Thereby, proud of cultural values, passed on to descendants to preserve and develop. However, cultural features have not been paid attention to comprehensively, many cultural characteristics are gradually in danger of disappearing. At the same time, the preservation of cultural values has not thoroughly dealt with outdated customs and superstitious ancient procedures. In addition, socio-economic development is in danger of eroding the unique characteristics of Hmong ethnic people, affecting their material and spiritual life.

4.3. Views on the government's support for the preservation of cultural heritage

The views of the interviewees showed that there needs to be a combination of local communities and state governments, from provincial to local levels and good coordination between government agencies to create strength for the process of preserving Hmong cultural values. This coordination is not only for the preservation process but also for planning and development purposes.

In the opinion of leaders of villages, villages and villages, the combination of local authorities and communities in cultural development has not been well matched. According to these individuals, local communities are less likely to participate in local development strategies, such as providing input to government projects or plans, monitoring development in the area and nearby sites, and especially in land planning and use issues.

"Coordination between the government and local people is very limited, especially before implementing land use and land ownership. Many times, we don't know anything about this process so when the project started, conflicts occurred. We have reported this to local authorities but it has happened frequently." (village head, Son La province).

The interviewees said that local authorities need to pay more attention to planning and approving development projects, urban planning, improving management capacity and strategy. The rights and responsibilities of stakeholders in conservation work should also be clearly defined. Besides, the coordination between local authorities and communities needs to be improved.

"Local authorities should step up the provision of public utilities not only to preserve existing facilities but also for the benefit of the community." (village head, Cao Bang province).

"The government should facilitate effective coordination between departments, especially the planning board, culture board, tourism board, academic board and environment board. All officials in government agencies must have good knowledge and a background in preserving cultural values." (leader of commune, Lai Chau province).

Moreover, the lack of adequate regulations and guidelines for the preservation of cultural values in Hmong communities is one of the main obstacles to conservation. Many conservation activities take place without guidelines on the conservation of physical heritage as one respondent mentioned:

"Guidelines should be more detailed on development in local areas and development plans and projects should consider processes for preserving cultural heritage." (leader of Ha Giang province).

"As tourism and trade increase rapidly, development regulations and guidelines need to be combined with the preservation of heritage sites in each locality. In fact, the regulations in the community will be changed to be consistent and in line with the guidance provided by the government." (village head, Ha Giang province).

Sites for cultural heritage and ceremonial activities should be protected by the government. Do not allow commercial and other activities to distract from the cultural activities of the village.

"So far, the strategy has been primarily concerned with boosting economic activities and ignoring social and environmental aspects that lead to imbalances in urban development." (officials of Lai Chau province).

Thus, the issue related to the support of the authorities and the strategy of preserving cultural values was discussed quite clearly by the subjects. In general, the party and state have taken an interest in preserving cultural values for the Hmong community in northern Vietnam. However, the implementation process still has many limitations, coming from the combination of levels of government, the coordination between local communities and authorities, urban planning issues need to be managed more effectively and regulations and guidelines related to conservation need to be more detailed. In addition, there are suggestions that the strategies put in place need to promote more information and awareness to local people.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Discuss research results

The results of the study showed that the Hmong local community in the northern midlands and mountainous areas was aware of the cultural beauty and proud of the ethnic characteristics. The preservation of cultural values also receives support from all levels of government and local communities. However, the process of preserving Hmong cultural values in the northern region is facing many challenges due to rapidly increasing trade.

A number of strategies have been adopted to preserve Hmong cultural heritage with government support. This process is geared towards the maintenance of cultural heritage sites and ceremonial ceremonies. Moreover, the local government's program for the preservation of cultural heritage is said to be a positive strategy for preserving and promoting Hmong cultural beauty. The projects have attracted the participation of residents, local communities and commercial establishments.

However, there are still limitations in preserving cultural values for the Hmong community in the northern midlands and mountainous areas of Vietnam. Some cultural aspects are not given enough attention, partly because they do not appear much in people's lives, on the other hand are sharpened worn by interbreeding and introduction with other cultures. Moreover, the issue of preserving cultural values needs to be considered and dealt with more thoroughly than the preservation of outdated and ancient procedures, causing adverse effects on the health, cultural image and economic development activities of the Hmong ethnic community.

The conservation process is still inefficient and thorough because the strategy is not clear and appropriate enough. The guidelines from the government are also not detailed and transparent enough about implementation. Regulatory guidance is an important tool in effectively implementing policies, similar to strategies related to preserving indigenous cultural values for the Hmong people living in the northern midlands and mountainous areas.

5.2. Solution

On the basis of research results, the author offers some solutions as follows:

First, strengthen party leadership and state control over ethnic minority cultural activities. Thereby controlling and limiting cultural activities that go against fine customs and customs, affecting the material and spiritual life of ethnic minorities.

Secondly, the northern provinces need to promote investment in harmonious and balanced resources between economic resources and cultural development resources for Hmong people. At the same time, investing heavily in the field of ethnic minority culture, so that culture can promote its role as an internal force to help people develop and keep up with the general development trend of the province.

Third, diversify forms of propaganda to sensitize ethnic minorities about their role and position in cultural identity and the need to maintain and promote their cultural identity.

Fourth, build a cultural work team strong enough in quantity and quality to successfully carry out the task of cultural development in general, preservation, promotion and cultural development of ethnic minorities in particular.

Fifth, enhance the intellectual level of ethnic minorities so that they can best fulfill their role as agents of maintaining and promoting the state's traditional cultural and cultural identity. The Party and the State should recognize the contributions of artisans to preserve their identity and encourage them to: Continue to explore,

collect, create, add unique and diverse features to each type of cultural heritage. At the same time, participate in teaching young people to inherit and promote the traditional cultural heritage of the country.

Sixth, paying attention to building and developing heritage movements is also a task that has practical effects in preserving and promoting the values of cultural heritages. It is necessary to establish mass art teams in localities and clubs to preserve national culture because this is also an appropriate form for people to participate in preserving and promoting their national cultural heritages in the best and most practical way.

Seventh, restore some unique traditional festivals or "dramatize" cultural performances to serve the people and gradually promote the effect so that the people of all ethnic groups in the province plan to enrich the cultural and spiritual life of the people.

5.3. Future nc limits and orientations

Besides the achievements, research has certain limitations. Firstly, Vietnam is a country with 54 ethnic groups living together, however, the research context only focuses on the cultural values of the Hmong ethnic community. Therefore, the current research results are not highly representative. Further studies can explore the topic of preserving the cultural values of the Vietnamese nation. Second, limitations relate to research modalities. Qualitative research conducted interviews with village elders, village heads, commune and district leaders. Therefore, the results of the study are highly subjective. Future studies may include in-depth interviews with people in the Hmong ethnic community. From there, make more objective judgments. At the same time, due to difficult geographical conditions and limited study time, the sample of observations of the study stopped at only 245 observations. To overcome this, further studies can extend the study period, thereby, discovering more novelties in the future.

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